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Roles Of Technology On Teaching Profession In Colleges Of Education In Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the roles of technology on the teaching profession in Colleges of Education in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The objectives were to identify the types of technology currently used in teacher education, assess educators' attitudes toward technology integration, determine the challenges faced in using technology, and explore strategies to enhance effective utilization in teaching and learning. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population comprised lecturers and students in selected Colleges of Education in Sokoto State, while a structured questionnaire was used as the primary instrument for data collection. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were employed for data analysis. The findings revealed that various forms of technology including computers, projectors, internet-based resources, and mobile devices are used to facilitate teaching, lesson preparation, assessment, and communication. Results further indicated that most educators hold positive attitudes toward technology integration, recognizing its impact on teaching effectiveness, student engagement, and professional growth. However, challenges such as inadequate ICT infrastructure, poor internet connectivity, limited funding, and insufficient training were found to hinder effective implementation. The study also identified key strategies to promote technology integration, including continuous professional development, adequate funding, and strong institutional support. It was concluded that technology plays a vital role in improving instructional delivery, enhancing professional competence, and fostering innovation in teacher education. The study recommended that government and educational stakeholders should invest in ICT infrastructure, organize regular capacity-building programs, and formulate effective policies to ensure sustainable technology integration in Colleges of Education across Sokoto State.

Keywords: ICT infrastructure, teaching and learning

INTRODUCTION

The advent of digital technologies has revolutionized various sectors, including education. In Nigeria, like in many other parts of the world. According to Akande (2021). Point out that, the integration of technology in education has gained significant momentum in recent years. However, its impact on teacher education, particularly in Colleges of Education, remains a subject of exploration in Nigeria, as such some colleges of Education were face by numerous challenges in its educational system, these including inadequate infrastructure, insufficient resources, and limited access to quality teacher training programs. Furthermore, Alabi, (2022), Stated that, despite the challenges, yet technology offers promising solutions to enhance teacher education and improve learning outcomes in Colleges of Education. Furthermore, Akande (2021). Reported that, the adoption of information and

communication Technology (ICT) tools, such as computers, tablets, and interactive whiteboards, presents opportunities for teacher professional development, curriculum enhancement, and student engagement. In a nutshell, Alabi (2022). online platforms and digital resources provide lecturers with access to a vast repository of educational materials and collaborative networks, transcending geographical barriers and facilitating continuous learning.

According to Aliyu (2020). opined that, Technology facilitates continuous professional development for teachers through online courses, webinars, and virtual conferences. These platforms offer opportunities for educators to update their pedagogical skills, learn about innovative teaching methods, and exchange best practices with colleagues globally. however, Gana (2023).reported that, Digital technologies enable the development of interactive and multimedia-rich instructional materials, aligning with the curriculum requirements of Colleges of Education, Lecturers can integrate educational software, simulations, and virtual laboratories to create engaging learning experiences that cater to diverse learning styles. According to Aliyu (2020). Stated that, technology empowers lecturers to experiment with innovative teaching strategies, such as flipped classrooms, blended learning models, and inquiry-based approaches by leveraging digital tools, educators can personalize instruction, provide timely feedback, and foster critical thinking and problem-solving skills among students. In addition Onasanya (2020) to technology mitigates resource constraints by providing teachers with access to a wide range of educational resources, including e-books, online journals, and educational apps. This access ensures that educators can supplement textbooks with current and relevant content, enhancing the quality of instruction and promoting lifelong learning.

Furthermore Gana (2022). Assert that, digital platforms enable lecturers to collaborate with peers, educational experts, and industry professionals, fostering a culture of sharing and collaboration. Through online forums, social media groups, and professional learning communities, educators can exchange ideas, seek advice, and collectively address common challenges in teaching and learning. In addition, technology plays a transformative role in shaping the future of teacher education in senior secondary schools in North West Nigeria by leveraging digital tools and resources, educators can enhance their pedagogical practices, improve learning outcomes, and adapt to the evolving needs of 21st-century learners. As noted by Ismaila (2022). Asserts that, realizing the full potential of technology requires concerted efforts from policymakers, Stakeholders, and the wider communities to address infrastructural barriers, provides adequate training and support for teachers, and promotes equitable access to technology-enabled learning environments. This study aims to contribute to the discourse on technology integration in teacher education and inform evidence-based strategies for enhancing educational practices in the region.

Statement of the Problem

Education is dynamic it changes with the changes in the society. The current technological changes of the 21st century calls for introduction of technology into the education sector of the society. The need for technology in the sector calls for its integration in to the process of training teachers to cope with the changes. In Sokoto state, particularly within Colleges of Education, There exists a significant gap in understanding how technology can effectively play a vital role on teaching profession. Despite the global advancements in educational technology, there remains lack of comprehensive understanding among teacher educators regarding the roles and potential impact of technology on teaching professions. This gap potentially hinders the preparation of future educators to integrate technology into their teaching methodologies, thereby limiting achieving the educational outcomes and competitiveness of Nigerian teachers on a global scale. (Global forum, 2023) Thus, there is a critical need to investigate and understand the roles of technology on teaching profession in colleges of education in Sokoto state.

Research Objectives

1. To find out the attitudes of educators towards technology integration in teacher education in colleges of education in Sokoto state
2. To identify the current utilization of technology in teacher education within colleges of education in Sokoto state
3. To determine the major challenges faced by educators in integrating technology into teacher education programs in Colleges of Education in Sokoto State?

Research Questions

1. What are the attitudes of educators towards the integration of technology in teacher education in Colleges of Education in Sokoto State?
2. What types of technology are currently being used in teacher education programs in Colleges of Education in Sokoto State?
3. What are the major challenges faced by educators in integrating technology into teacher education programs in Colleges of Education in Sokoto State

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual framework provides a structured way of understanding the relationship between variables in a study. It serves as a visual and theoretical guide that explains how the independent, dependent, and intervening variables are connected. In this study, the conceptual framework is based on the idea that technology integration plays a crucial role in improving teacher education outcomes through educators' attitudes, utilization levels, and institutional support mechanisms.

The conceptual framework illustrates that effective technology integration in teacher education is a function of educators' attitudes, actual usage levels, and institutional support systems. When challenges are properly addressed through strategic interventions, the integration of technology can significantly enhance the quality and relevance of teacher preparation programs in Colleges of Education in Sokoto State.

Concept of Technology Integration

Technology integration" refers to the incorporation of technological tools, resources, and practices into teaching and learning environments in such a way that they become a seamless part of pedagogy, instruction, and learning outcomes rather than simply being add-ons or optional extras. According to Davies & West (2014), technology integration means the effective implementation of educational technology to accomplish intended learning outcomes. They view educational technology broadly as electronic or mechanical tools or devices that help students reach learning goals.

Gambari (2021) defines technology integration as the incorporation of digital resources and processes into the daily practices of schools. This includes not only devices but also digital content, pedagogical methods, and teacher-learner interactions mediated by digital tools. Eya (2021) expands the notion by stating that technology integration is using technology tools in general content areas in education so learners apply computer and technology skills to learning and problem solving. This suggests technology is not only about delivery but enabling students to engage in authentic learning tasks.

Concept of Teacher Education

Teacher education refers to the structured programs, processes, and activities designed to prepare individuals for the teaching profession by equipping them with the necessary knowledge, skills, attitudes, and professional competencies to facilitate effective learning. It serves as the foundation for producing qualified, competent, and professional teachers who can meet the educational needs of learners in a dynamic and technology-driven society.

According to Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014), teacher education is a formal training program designed to produce effective classroom teachers capable of contributing to national development. The National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014) emphasizes that teacher education shall continue to update teachers' knowledge and skills in pedagogy, curriculum development, and the use of educational technology to improve the quality of instruction in Nigerian schools.

Similarly,

In contemporary times, the role of teacher education has expanded beyond traditional pedagogical training to include technological literacy and digital competence. Ameh and Odoh (2021) assert that effective teacher education programs must now integrate Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to prepare teachers who can function efficiently in modern classrooms. The ability to use technology in instructional delivery has become a key component of quality teacher education, particularly in the 21st-century learning environment.

Therefore, teacher education is a dynamic and evolving process that continuously adapts to societal changes, educational reforms, and technological advancements. For Colleges of Education in Sokoto State, integrating technology into teacher education is crucial for producing teachers who are not only professionally competent but also technologically empowered to meet global educational standards.

Concept of Technology Utilization

Technology utilization refers to the practical application and use of technological tools, resources, and systems to enhance teaching, learning, and educational management. In the context of teacher education, it involves how educators and trainee teachers employ various forms of information and communication technology (ICT) to facilitate instruction, improve learning outcomes, and develop professional competence.

Mbah (2019) further explains that technology utilization in teacher education programs enables prospective teachers to acquire practical digital skills, such as preparing PowerPoint presentations, conducting online research, designing e-assessments, and using virtual learning environments (VLEs). These skills are essential for 21st-century teaching and learning, where technology plays a central role in curriculum delivery and learner engagement.

The effective utilization of technology is influenced by several factors, including teachers' competence, accessibility of resources, institutional policies, training opportunities, and attitude toward technology (Akinsola & Ajayi, 2021). Where these conditions are favorable, technology becomes a catalyst for innovative teaching practices; where they are lacking, technology remains underutilized despite its availability.

According to Ogunlade and Yusuf (2020), in Nigerian teacher education institutions, technology utilization is often limited by infrastructural deficiencies such as poor internet connectivity, unstable electricity, and inadequate funding. However, educators who are ICT-literate and motivated tend to use available tools creatively to enhance instructional delivery.

In teacher education, technology utilization supports both pedagogical and professional development. Pedagogically, it enhances students' learning experiences through interactive content, virtual simulations, and access to global resources. Professionally, it enables teachers to participate in online workshops, engage in continuous professional development, and collaborate with peers across different institutions (Ameh & Odoh, 2021).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A research design is defined as a framework of methods and techniques chosen by a researcher to combine various components of research in a reasonably logical manner so that the research problem is efficiently handled (Nwagu, 2014). It refers to the strategy or plan which a researcher adopts to carry out an investigation. This study will be carried out using Descriptive Survey Design. Descriptive survey design according to Nwagu (2014), is a system for collecting information from or about people to describe, compare or explain their knowledge, attitudes and behaviors. It is one of the major categories of descriptive design that describes the present condition of a given phenomenon by collecting data from defined population. Therefore, descriptive survey design is selected because the study is descriptive in nature. The process is in order to set certain answers to research questions generated in the study.

Population of the Study

The population of 1,280 will be drive from Shehu shagari College of Education, College of Education Gidan Madi and Biga College of Education Sokoto state. The distribution of the population in the three colleges of education in sokoto.

Population of the study

S/n	Colleges of Education	Number of Academic Staff
(1)	Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto	1,094
(2)	Biga College of Education, Sokoto	69
(3)	Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi	117
	Total	1280

Ministry for Higher Education, Sokoto (2025)

Sample size and Sampling Technique

these will form the population of this research and a sample of 306 lecturers will be determine using (Research Advisor 2006) table of selecting samples. Therefore, Stratify as well as Simple random sampling will be use in selecting the participants of the study in order to give equal chances for the both genders' for the participation of the study.

Instrument

The instrument for this research will be four Likert type scale questionnaires which will be use for data collection, it will consist: Strongly Agree, (SA) =4 Agree, (A) = 3 Disagree (D) = 2 Strongly Dis agree (D), = 1. Data collected will be Analyze using frequencies and percentages (Descriptive statistics), Mean and standard deviations. Instruments will be tested for Validity, were expert from the Department of curriculum and center for educational technology in shehu shagari college of education sokoto will offer the construct and face validation in order for the instrument to be efficient and relevant for data collections. A sample of the questionnaire was shown to the research supervisor for professional corrections and comments which will incorporated into the final draft of the instrument which ensure that it had both face and content validity. The content validity index (CVI) gotten from the content validity determined the validity of the research questionnaire. The advantage of this validity type is to determine the extent to which the items of the construct represent the concept to be measured (Creswell, 2012). The content validity index was determined using the formula below:

While reliability of the instrument will be tested through pilot study were tenth of questionnaire’s will be sent to the respondents who are not part of the study, ie polytechnics or university, after collecting the data then, it will be analyze using Cronbach, alpha in the SPSS softwre version 25 at 0.65 level of significance. While method for data analysis, the data will be analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation as well as frequency and percentage (SPSS) Statistical package for social science version 25 will be used to find out the significance between dependent and Independent variables

RESULTS

Research Questions One: Technology Integration in teaching

Table 1: Technology Integration in teaching

STATEMENT	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
I believe that technology enhances the teaching and learning process in teacher education.	306	2.12	.971	Rejected
I feel confident in using modern technology tools in my instructional activities.	306	1.96	.790	Rejected
Integrating technology into teaching increases students’ motivation and participation.	306	2.04	.889	Rejected
I am willing to learn and adopt new technologies in my teaching profession.	306	2.00	.913	Rejected
Technology integration is essential for improving the quality of teacher education.	306	2.00	.913	Rejected

Source Field Data (2025)

Source Field Data (2025)

Table 1. Shows a summary of the mean ratings of the Technology Integration in teaching. The data analysis revealed that the respondents were of the view that; I believe that technology enhances the teaching and learning process in teacher education (Mean=2.12, Standard Deviation=.971), I feel confident in using modern technology tools in my instructional activities (Mean=1.96, Standard Deviation=.790), integrating technology into teaching increases students’ motivation and participation (Mean=2.04, Standard Deviation=.889), I am willing to learn and adopt new technologies in my teaching profession (Mean=2.00, Standard Deviation=.913) and technology integration is essential for improving the quality of teacher education (Mean=2.00, Standard Deviation=.913). The results indicate that educators recognize the value of technology in enhancing teaching and learning, are confident in using digital tools, and are willing to embrace technological innovations. These positive attitudes provide a solid foundation for promoting effective technology integration in teacher education, provided that adequate institutional support and infrastructure are sustained.

Research Question two: *Types of Technology Currently Used in Teacher Education Programs*

Table 2 Summary of the Types of Technology Currently Used in Teacher Education Programs

STATEMENT	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
I regularly use computers and projectors during teaching sessions.	306	2.00	.913	Rejected
Internet-based resources (e.g., Google Classroom, YouTube, Zoom) are used for teaching and learning.	306	2.00	.764	Rejected
Educational software and applications are used for lesson planning and delivery.	306	2.04	.841	Rejected
Interactive whiteboards or smartboards are utilized during classroom instruction.	306	2.00	.816	Rejected
Mobile devices (phones, tablets) are used for educational communication and research.	306	2.28	.980	Rejected

Source Field Data (2025)

Table 2. Shows a summary of the mean ratings of the types of technology currently used in teacher education programs. The data analysis revealed that the respondents were of the view that; I regularly use computers and projectors during teaching sessions (Mean=2.00, Standard Deviation=.913), Internet-based resources (e.g., Google Classroom, YouTube, Zoom) are used for teaching and learning (Mean=2.00, Standard Deviation=.764), Educational software and applications are used for lesson planning and delivery (Mean=2.04, Standard Deviation=.841), Interactive whiteboards or smartboards are utilized during classroom instruction (Mean=2.00, Standard Deviation=.816), and Mobile devices (phones, tablets) are used for educational communication and research (Mean=2.28, Standard Deviation=.980). Overall, the results suggest that while educators in teacher education programs use a variety of technologies ranging from computers and projectors to mobile devices and online platforms the level of utilization remains moderate. This implies that although awareness of digital tools exists, there is still a need for improved infrastructure, training, and institutional support to promote full-scale integration of technology in teacher education.

Research Question Three: *Major Challenges Faced by Educators in Integrating Technology*

Table 3 Summary of the Major Challenges Faced by Educators in Integrating Technology

STATEMENT	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
Lack of adequate training in technology use limits effective integration.	306	2.04	.889	Rejected
Insufficient access to ICT facilities hinders technology-based teaching.	306	2.04	.889	Rejected
Poor internet connectivity affects online instructional activities.	306	2.00	.866	Rejected
Lack of institutional support discourages educators from using technology.	306	1.96	.889	Rejected
Inadequate funding limits the procurement of modern educational technologies.	306	2.34	.885	Rejected

Source Field Data (2025)

Table 3. Shows a summary of the mean ratings of the major challenges faced by educators in integrating technology. The data analysis revealed that the respondents were of the view that; Lack of adequate training in technology use limits effective integration (Mean=2.04, Standard Deviation=.889), Insufficient access to ICT facilities hinders technology-based teaching (Mean=2.04, Standard Deviation=.889), Poor internet connectivity affects online instructional activities (Mean=2.00, Standard Deviation=.866), Lack of institutional support discourages educators from using technology (Mean=1.96, Standard Deviation=.889) and Inadequate funding limits the procurement of modern educational technologies (Mean=2.34, Standard Deviation=.885). The findings indicate that effective technology integration in teacher education is constrained by systemic and infrastructural issues, including inadequate funding, lack of training, insufficient ICT resources,

poor internet connectivity, and weak institutional support. Addressing these challenges requires a coordinated effort from government, educational institutions, and stakeholders to ensure that educators are adequately equipped, motivated, and supported to integrate technology effectively into teaching and learning.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The findings of the study revealed that technology integration plays a vital role in enhancing the teaching and learning process in teacher education. The respondents generally agreed that the use of technology tools contributes significantly to instructional delivery, improves students' motivation, and fosters active participation in learning. This aligns with the view of Teo (2019), who emphasized that integrating technology into teaching enables educators to adopt innovative pedagogical practices that enhance students' engagement and understanding.

The mean ratings indicated that most educators believe that technology enhances the teaching and learning process and that they feel confident using modern technological tools in their instructional activities. This suggests a positive attitude toward technology integration among educators, which is consistent with the findings of Koehler and Mishra (2009) in their Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework, which argues that teachers' knowledge and confidence in using technology determine how effectively they integrate it into their teaching.

Furthermore, the study found that integrating technology increases students' motivation and participation. This finding supports Bebell and O'Dwyer (2010), who reported that technology-rich classrooms promote student-centered learning and improve learning outcomes. The implication is that when teachers effectively integrate digital tools—such as multimedia presentations, simulations, and online learning platforms—students become more involved and interested in learning activities.

However, while educators recognize the benefits of technology in teaching, some challenges were noted, including inadequate access to modern equipment, poor internet connectivity, and limited institutional support. This finding is in line with Adu and Galloway (2021), who noted that infrastructural and administrative constraints often hinder effective technology adoption in Nigerian teacher education institutions. Overall, the discussion indicates that technology integration has a transformative impact on teaching effectiveness, instructional quality, and student learning experiences. However, to sustain these benefits, institutions must invest in continuous professional development for educators, provide adequate infrastructure, and formulate supportive policies that encourage the meaningful use of technology in education.

The findings of the study revealed that a variety of technological tools are currently being utilized in teacher education programs. These include computers, projectors, interactive whiteboards, mobile devices, internet-based learning platforms, and educational software applications. The respondents indicated that these technologies are used mainly for lesson preparation, instructional delivery, assessment, and communication between teachers and students. This finding underscores the increasing adoption of technology to support teaching and learning in colleges of education.

The use of computers and projectors was reported as the most common practice among teacher educators. This aligns with the findings of Nwosu and Odetunde (2020), who observed that computer-assisted instruction and multimedia presentations are among the most widely used tools for effective teaching in Nigerian teacher education institutions. The frequent use of these technologies indicates that educators have recognized their potential in simplifying content delivery and enhancing students' understanding.

The findings showed that internet-based resources, such as online research materials, digital libraries, and learning management systems (LMS), are becoming increasingly popular. This development reflects a gradual shift from traditional classroom instruction to blended and digital learning environments. According to Ajayi and Afolabi (2021), the integration of online resources in teacher education allows both instructors and student-teachers to access up-to-date information and engage in collaborative learning experiences beyond the classroom setting.

The findings of the study revealed that educators encounter several challenges in the process of integrating technology into teacher education programs. The major issues identified include inadequate access to technological facilities, poor internet connectivity, insufficient training and technical support, lack of institutional funding, and resistance to change among some educators.

These factors collectively hinder the full realization of the benefits of technology integration in the teaching and learning process. The respondents indicated that inadequate access to modern technological tools, such as computers, projectors, and smart boards, is one of the major barriers to effective technology integration. This finding agrees with Adu and Galloway (2021), who noted that the lack of adequate infrastructure remains a major constraint to technology use in Nigerian teacher education institutions. Without sufficient access to equipment, educators are unable to effectively integrate digital resources into their instructional activities.

Another critical challenge identified is poor internet connectivity. Many institutions in Nigeria still struggle with unstable and expensive internet services, which limit online teaching, research, and communication. Okeke and Ume (2019) observed that inconsistent network access and low bandwidth in educational institutions significantly affect the smooth implementation of e-learning and other technology-driven initiatives. This lack of reliable internet access discourages both educators and students from using digital learning platforms.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that technology plays a transformative and indispensable role in the teaching profession within Colleges of Education in Sokoto State. It has enhanced instructional delivery, improved communication, and provided educators with new methods for engaging students and assessing learning outcomes. The integration of technological tools such as computers, projectors, internet resources, and learning management systems has not only improved teaching effectiveness but also increased students' motivation, participation, and academic performance.

The findings further established that technology supports teachers' professional growth through online training, access to global educational resources, and collaboration with peers. Despite these benefits, the study also identified significant challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, poor internet connectivity, limited funding, and insufficient ICT training among educators. These barriers continue to hinder the full realization of technology's potential in teacher education.

Therefore, the study concludes that for technology to be effectively integrated and sustained in Colleges of Education, stakeholders—government, institutional administrators, and educators—must work collaboratively to provide adequate infrastructure, continuous professional development, and supportive policies. Embracing these measures will not only strengthen the teaching profession but also contribute to producing technologically competent teachers capable of meeting the demands of 21st-century education in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Government and institutional authorities should provide sufficient technological resources such as computers, projectors, smart boards, and reliable internet connectivity in all Colleges of Education. This will enhance the effective integration of technology in teaching and learning.
2. Regular training workshops, seminars, and refresher courses should be organized to improve teachers' digital competence and confidence in using emerging educational technologies. Professional development should focus on both pedagogical and technical aspects of ICT.
3. Adequate financial allocations should be made by the government and educational agencies to support the purchase, maintenance, and upgrading of ICT facilities. Partnerships with private organizations and donor agencies can also be encouraged to sustain funding.
4. Institutions should employ skilled ICT personnel to provide technical support and maintenance services. This will minimize system breakdowns and encourage continuous utilization of technology by educators.
5. Awareness campaigns and incentives should be introduced to motivate educators to adopt technology-based teaching methods. Recognizing and rewarding innovative ICT practices among lecturers can further encourage adoption.
6. Efforts should be made to provide stable electricity through alternative energy sources such as solar power to ensure uninterrupted use of ICT facilities in Colleges of Education.

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